

Supplementary Figures for “Molecular and morphological baraminology of Xenarthra”

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Supplementary Figure 1. Silhouette plot of the character data set from Billet et al., 2011. The data shows two clear clusters of size 17 and 5 in red and green, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 2. Silhouette plot of the character data set from Gaudin, 2004. The data shows two clear clusters of size 32 and 7 in red and green, respectively.

Supplementary Figure 3. Three-dimensional multidimensional scaling plot showing the baraminic relationship between 39 taxa from the Gaudin data set. Seven armadillo species are shown in green, whereas 32 sloth species are shown in red, with somewhat of a separation between some of the sloth species.

Supplementary Figure 4. Elbow plot for sequence identity matrix from the analysis of the mtDNA sequences.

Supplementary Figure 5. Silhouette plot for sequence identity matrix from the analysis of the mtDNA sequences.